

A Calculus for Attribute-based Memory Updates (Supplementary Material)

Marino Miculan and Michele Pasqua

Dept. of Mathematics, Computer Science and Physics - University of Udine (Italy)
(marino.miculan|michele.pasqua)@uniud.it

Technical report with the supplementary material of the paper “A Calculus for Attribute-based Memory Updates” [1].

1 Proofs of Section 3

Proof of Proposition 1. For this proposition we give a simple sketch of the proof.

Proposition 1 (Termination of the wave semantics)

Proof (Sketch). The proof relies on the following observation: each discovered update cannot be considered twice, within the same discovery phase. When an update `upd` is executed and, at the same time, it is removed from the execution pool, if the ECA dependency graph is acyclic then another instance of `upd` cannot be inserted again in the pool, during the discovery phase originated by `upd`. This ensures that the number of updates to execute (after all possible discovery phases) is finite and hence, eventually, the execution pool becomes empty, meaning that a stable system is reached.

2 Proofs of Section 4

Proof of Theorem 1. In order to prove the theorem, we need some supporting lemmas and some preliminary notions. Given a AbU system $S = R_1 \langle \Sigma_1, \Theta_1 \rangle \parallel \dots \parallel R_n \langle \Sigma_n, \Theta_n \rangle$, we denote with $S[R'_k \langle \Sigma'_k, \Theta'_k \rangle \gg R_k \langle \Sigma_k, \Theta_k \rangle]$, for $k \in [1..n]$, the system S where $R_k \langle \Sigma_k, \Theta_k \rangle$ is replaced by $R'_k \langle \Sigma'_k, \Theta'_k \rangle$. We use the same notation for replacing AbC components, namely we denote with $C[\Gamma_k : P_k \gg \Gamma'_k : P'_k]$, for $k \in [1..n]$, the component $C = \Gamma_1 : P_1 \parallel \dots \parallel \Gamma_n : P_n$ where $\Gamma_k : P_k$ is replaced by $\Gamma'_k : P'_k$. Given an AbC component $C = \Gamma_1 : P_1 \parallel \dots \parallel \Gamma_n : P_n$, the translation functions \mathcal{T}^h , with $h \in [1..n]$, retrieve all the auxiliary resources, in particular all *rule flags*, needed to model the behavior of the processes P_h (see Section 4 of [1]). The functions \mathcal{T}^h are inductively defined on the structure of each P_h . In particular, there is a one-to-one correspondence between the AbC process' instances in P_h and the generated AbU rules (see again Section 4 of [1]). The latter, have an unique rule flag, of the form $P_h r_i$, with $h \in [1..n]$ and $i \geq 0$. Hence, for each *residual* process P'_h of P_h , i.e., a process we can obtain applying zero or more times the rewriting semantics of AbC, we can associate a *firing rule firing*(P'_h), namely the rule flag that must be active, in order to execute the

process P'_h . Note that, P_h is a residual of P_h itself. The notion of residual can be extended to components: C' is a residual of C if we can obtain C' applying zero or more times the rewriting semantics of AbC to C . We can then define the firing rules set $\text{firing}(C')$ of the residual component $C' = \Gamma'_1 : P'_1 \parallel \dots \parallel \Gamma'_n : P'_n$ as $\{\text{firing}(P'_h) \mid h \in [1..n]\}$. Note that, $\text{firing}(C) = \{\text{firing}(P_1), \dots, \text{firing}(P_n)\} = \{P_1 r_0, \dots, P_n r_0\}$, by definition.

Definition 1 (Firing AbU system). A AbU system $S = R_1 \langle \Sigma_1, \Theta_1 \rangle \parallel \dots \parallel R_n \langle \Sigma_n, \Theta_n \rangle$ is firing for the AbC component $C' = \Gamma'_1 : P'_1 \parallel \dots \parallel \Gamma'_n : P'_n$, residual of C , when all the following hold, for each $k \in [1..n]$:

- $\text{firing}(P'_k) = P_h r_i$
- $\Sigma_k(P_h r_i) = \text{tt}$
- $\text{DefUpds}(R_k, \{P_h r_i\}, \Sigma_k) \cup \text{LocalUpds}(R_k, \{P_h r_i\}, \Sigma_k) \subseteq \Theta_k$
- $\text{ExtTasks}(R_k, \{P_h r_i\}, \Sigma_k) = \text{task}_1 \dots \text{task}_m$
- $\forall j \in [1..n] \setminus \{k\}. \{[\text{act}] \Sigma_j \mid \exists l \in [1..m]. \text{task}_l = @\varphi : \text{act} \wedge \Sigma_j \models \varphi\} \subseteq \Theta_j$

Proposition 1. We can formulate the following observations, assuming a component $C = \Gamma_1 : P_1 \parallel \dots \parallel \Gamma_n : P_n$ of AbC and a AbU system $S = R_1 \langle \Sigma_1, \Theta_1 \rangle \parallel \dots \parallel R_n \langle \Sigma_n, \Theta_n \rangle$, such that $R_i = \mathcal{T}^i(P_i)$ for $i \in [1..n]$.

- A Let $\Gamma : P$ be a residual of $\Gamma_i : P_i$, with $i \in [1..n]$, and e an expression. If $\Sigma_i \succeq \Gamma : P$ and $\llbracket e \rrbracket(\Gamma_i) = v$, for some v , then $\llbracket \mathcal{T}(e) \rrbracket(\Sigma_i) = v$.
- B Let $\Gamma : P$ be a residual of $\Gamma_i : P_i$, with $i \in [1..n]$, and Π a predicate. If $\Sigma_i \succeq \Gamma : P$, $\Gamma \models \Pi[v/x]$, for some v , and $\Sigma_i(\text{msg}) = v$, then $\Sigma_i \models \text{Repl}(\mathcal{T}(\Pi), x)$.
- C Let $C' = \Gamma'_1 : P'_1 \parallel \dots \parallel \Gamma'_n : P'_n$ be residual of C , $\Gamma'_1 : P'_1 \xrightarrow{\delta} \Gamma''_1 : P''_1$, for some AbC process label δ , and $S \succeq C'$. If $S \rightarrow^* S'$, for some $S' = R_1 \langle \Sigma'_1, \Theta'_1 \rangle \parallel \dots \parallel R_n \langle \Sigma'_n, \Theta'_n \rangle$, by executing the AbU rule translation of P'_1 , then no updates on attributes of Γ'_i on the AbU node i , for $i \in [2..n]$, are performed and no rule flags on the AbU node i , with $i \in [2..n]$, are modified. In other words: $\Sigma_i(a) = \Sigma'_i(a)$, for all attributes a of Γ'_i , with $i \in [2..n]$; and $\Sigma_i(P_k r_j) = \Sigma'_i(P_k r_j)$, for all $i \in [2..n]$, $k \in [1..n]$ and $j \geq 0$.
- D Let $\Gamma'_i : P'_i$ and $\Gamma'_j : P'_j$ be residuals of $\Gamma_i : P_i$ and $\Gamma_j : P_j$, respectively, with $i, j \in [1..n]$, and Π a predicate. If $\Sigma_i \succeq \Gamma'_i : P'_i$, $\Sigma_j \succeq \Gamma'_j : P'_j$, $\llbracket \Pi \rrbracket(\Gamma'_i) = \Pi'$ and $\Gamma'_j \models \Pi'$, then $\Sigma_j \models \llbracket \text{Ext}(\mathcal{T}(\Pi)) \rrbracket \Sigma_i$.

Proof. Observations A and B are trivial, they hold by definition of the translation function \mathcal{T} . For the observation C, we can note, by the definition of \mathcal{T} , that each action in the translated rule originated from P'_1 is local, hence all modifications are on the current node 1. This means that no updates on attributes and rule flags are made on other nodes i , with $i \in [2..n]$. The only rules updating external nodes are the *send* rules, with the action $\overline{\text{msg}} \leftarrow \mathcal{T}(e)$, which modifies a state in a node i such that $i \in [2..n]$. But, msg is an auxiliary resource introduced by the translation, it is not an attribute of any Γ_i , with $i \in [2..n]$, nor a rule flag of any i , with $i \in [2..n]$. Finally, for the observation D, we have that $\llbracket \Pi \rrbracket(\Gamma'_i)$ substitutes the instances **this.a** with $\Gamma'_i(a) = v$ in Π , and lets untouched the instances a . Instead, $\text{Ext}(\Pi)$ substitutes the instances of a not prefixed by **this**.

(in Π) with \bar{a} (and then apply the translation \mathcal{T}). It is easy to note that in $\Gamma'_j \models \Pi'$ each original instance of `this.a` in Π now takes the value $\Gamma'_i(a)$ and each instance of a takes the value $\Gamma'_j(a)$. Similarly, in $\Sigma_j \models \{\text{Ext}(\mathcal{T}(\Pi))\} \Sigma_i$ each original instance of `this.a` in Π takes the value $\Sigma_i(a)$ and each instance of a takes the value $\Sigma_j(a)$. But, by the observation $\underline{\mathbf{A}}$, we have that $\Gamma'_i(a) = \Sigma_i(a)$ and $\Gamma'_j(a) = \Sigma_j(a)$.

Lemma 1. *Consider a AbC component $C = \Gamma_1 : P_1 \parallel \dots \parallel \Gamma_n : P_n$ and a AbU system $\mathbf{S} = R_1 \langle \Sigma_1, \Theta_1 \rangle \parallel \dots \parallel R_n \langle \Sigma_n, \Theta_n \rangle$, such that $R_i = \mathcal{T}^i(P_i)$, for $i \in [1..n]$. Let $C' = \Gamma'_1 : P'_1 \parallel \dots \parallel \Gamma'_n : P'_n$ be a residual of C such that $\mathbf{S} \succeq C'$ and \mathbf{S} is firing for C' . Let $\Gamma : P$ be a component of C' , namely $\Gamma : P = \Gamma'_k : P'_k$, for $k \in [1..n]$. Then, for all Γ', P' such that $\Gamma : P \xrightarrow{\delta} \Gamma' : P'$, for some δ , there exists a AbU system $\mathbf{S}' = R_1 \langle \Sigma'_1, \Theta'_1 \rangle \parallel \dots \parallel R_n \langle \Sigma'_n, \Theta'_n \rangle$ such that $\mathbf{S} \rightarrow^* \mathbf{S}'$, $\mathbf{S}' \succeq C''$ and \mathbf{S}' is firing for C'' , with $C'' = C'[\Gamma : P \gg \Gamma' : P']$.*

Proof. The only rule applicable is (COMP), namely $\Gamma : P \xrightarrow{\delta} \Gamma' : P'$ is obtained from $\Gamma : P \xrightarrow{\delta} \Gamma' : P'$. The proof is by induction on the derivation tree for $\Gamma : P \xrightarrow{\delta} \Gamma' : P'$. Depending on the last rule used in the derivation, we have the following cases.

Case (ZERO). Then: $\delta = \overline{\mathbf{ff}}(0)$; $P' = P = 0$; $\Gamma' = \Gamma$. Setting $\mathbf{S}' = \mathbf{S}$, we obtain trivially the conclusion, since $C' = C$.

Case (BRD). Then: $\delta = \overline{\Pi}(v)$, for some Π and v ; $P = \langle e @ \Pi \rangle . P''$, for some P'' , Π' such that $\{\Pi'\}(\Gamma) = \Pi$ and e such that $\llbracket e \rrbracket(\Gamma) = v$; $P' = P''$; $\Gamma' = \Gamma$. Let $P_h r_i = \text{firing}(P)$ be the firing rule of P and $j = \text{Next}(i)$. The translation of P generates the following AbU rule:

$$P_h r_i \triangleright P_h r_i \leftarrow \perp P_h r_j \leftarrow \top, @ (P_h r_i = \top \wedge \text{Ext}(\Pi)) : \overline{msg} \leftarrow \mathcal{T}(e) \quad (1)$$

We assumed that $\Gamma : P$ is the AbC component $\Gamma'_k : P'_k$ of C' , so we are on the node k of the AbU translation, i.e., $R_k \langle \Sigma_k, \Theta_k \rangle$. Since \mathbf{S} is firing for C' , we have that Θ_k contains the update $\text{upd} = (P_h r_i, \overline{\mathbf{ff}})(P_h r_j, \mathbf{tt})$, by definition of $\text{DefUpds}(R_k, \{P_h r_i\}, \Sigma_k)$. Since the rule in (1) is not local we have that $\text{LocalUpds}(R_k, \{P_h r_i\}, \Sigma_k) = \emptyset$. For the same reason, we have that $\text{ExtTasks}(R_k, \{P_h r_i\}, \Sigma_k) = T$, with $T = @(\text{Ext}(\Pi)) : \overline{msg} \leftarrow v$, given $\llbracket \mathcal{T}(e) \rrbracket \Sigma_k = v$ (justified by Prop. 1A). Furthermore, for all $w \in [1..n] \setminus \{k\}$ we have that Θ_w is a superset of $\{(msg, v) \mid \Sigma_w \models \text{Ext}(\Pi)\}$. When the AbU semantics evolves with the rule (STEP) applied to the system \mathbf{S} , performing an execution step (EXEC), the update upd is committed, obtaining $\Sigma'_k = \Sigma_k[\overline{\mathbf{ff}}/P_h r_i \ \mathbf{tt}/P_h r_j]$. The discovery phase launched during (STEP) computes $\Theta'_k = \Theta_k \setminus \{\text{upd}\} \cup \text{DefUpds}(R_k, \{P_h r_i, P_h r_j\}, \Sigma'_k) \cup \text{LocalUpds}(R_k, \{P_h r_i, P_h r_j\}, \Sigma'_k)$. By definition of \mathcal{T} , and $\text{Next}(i) = j$, we have that $\text{firing}(P'') = P_h r_j$. Hence, we have that Θ'_k is a superset of $\text{DefUpds}(R_k, \{P_h r_j\}, \Sigma'_k) \cup \text{LocalUpds}(R_k, \{P_h r_j\}, \Sigma'_k)$. The last two requirements of the Def. 1 are satisfied by the definition of (STEP), that guarantees to perform the discovery of $T' = \text{ExtTasks}(R_k, \{P_h r_i, P_h r_j\}, \Sigma_k)$ by applying the rule (Disc) with T' on all nodes $w \in [1..n] \setminus \{k\}$. This means that

$S' = S[R_k\langle \Sigma'_k, \Theta'_k \rangle \gg R_k\langle \Sigma_k, \Theta_k \rangle]$ is firing for C'' . Furthermore, no attributes of Γ are modified (only auxiliary resources added by the translation are involved in the update). Hence, we also have that $S' \succeq C''$, concluding the proof for this case.

Case (RCV). Then: $\delta = \Pi(v)$, for some Π such that $\Gamma \models \Pi$ and $v; P = (x \mid \Pi').P''$, for some P'' and Π' such that $\Gamma \models \Pi'[v/x]; P' = P''[v/x]; \Gamma' = \Gamma$. Let $P_{hr_i} = \text{firing}(P)$ be the firing rule of P and $j = \text{Next}(i)$. The translation of P generates the following AbU rule:

$$P_{hr_i} (P_{hr_i} = \top \wedge \text{Repl}(\mathcal{T}(\Pi), x)) : x \leftarrow \text{msg } P_{hr_i} \leftarrow \perp P_{hr_j} \leftarrow \top \quad (2)$$

We assumed that $\Gamma : P$ is the AbC component $\Gamma'_k : P'_k$ of C' , so we are on the node k of the AbU translation, i.e., $R_k\langle \Sigma_k, \Theta_k \rangle$. Since S is firing for C' , we have that Θ_k contains the update $\text{upd} = (x, v)(P_{hr_i}, \text{ff})(P_{hr_j}, \text{tt})$, by definition of $\text{LocalUpds}(R_k, \{P_{hr_i}\}, \Sigma_k)$, given $\Sigma_k(\text{msg}) = v$. Note that, the satisfiability of the condition $\text{Repl}(\mathcal{T}(\Pi), x)$ is guaranteed by Prop. 1B. Since the rule in (2) is local and it does not have default actions, we have that $\text{DefUpds}(R_k, \{P_{hr_i}\}, \Sigma_k) = \emptyset$ and $\text{ExtTasks}(R_k, \{P_{hr_i}\}, \Sigma_k) = \varepsilon$. When the AbU semantics evolves with the rule (STEP) applied to the system S , performing an execution step (EXEC), the update upd is committed, obtaining $\Sigma'_k = \Sigma_k[v/x \text{ ff}/P_{hr_i} \text{ tt}/P_{hr_j}]$. The discovery phase launched during (STEP) computes $\Theta'_k = \Theta_k \setminus \{\text{upd}\} \cup \text{DefUpds}(R_k, \{x, P_{hr_i}, P_{hr_j}\}, \Sigma'_k) \cup \text{LocalUpds}(R_k, \{x, P_{hr_i}, P_{hr_j}\}, \Sigma'_k)$. By definition of \mathcal{T} , and $\text{Next}(i) = j$, we have that $\text{firing}(P'') = P_{hr_j}$. Hence, we have that Θ'_k is a superset of $\text{DefUpds}(R_k, \{P_{hr_j}\}, \Sigma'_k) \cup \text{LocalUpds}(R_k, \{P_{hr_j}\}, \Sigma'_k)$. The last two requirements of the Def. 1 are satisfied by the definition of (STEP), that guarantees to perform the discovery of $T' = \text{ExtTasks}(R_k, \{x, P_{hr_i}, P_{hr_j}\}, \Sigma_k)$ by applying the rule (DISC) with T' on all nodes $w \in [1..n] \setminus \{k\}$. This means that $S' = S[R_k\langle \Sigma'_k, \Theta'_k \rangle \gg R_k\langle \Sigma_k, \Theta_k \rangle]$ is firing for C'' (the substitution $[v/x]$ in P'' is recorded by updating the resource x with the value v). Furthermore, no attributes of Γ are modified (only auxiliary resources added by the translation are involved in the update). Hence, we also have that $S' \succeq C''$, concluding the proof for this case.

Case (UPD). Then: $P = [a := e]P''$, for some P'' and $e; \Gamma' = \Gamma[v/a]'$, given $\llbracket e \rrbracket(\Gamma) = v$ and $\Gamma[v/a] : P'' \xrightarrow{\delta} \Gamma[v/a]' : P'$. Let $P_{hr_i} = \text{firing}(P)$ be the firing rule of P and $j = \text{Next}(i)$. The translation of P generates the following AbU rule:

$$P_{hr_i} (P_{hr_i} = \top) : a \leftarrow \mathcal{T}(e) P_{hr_i} \leftarrow \perp P_{hr_j} \leftarrow \top \quad (3)$$

We assumed that $\Gamma : P$ is the AbC component $\Gamma'_k : P'_k$ of C' , so we are on the node k of the AbU translation, i.e., $R_k\langle \Sigma_k, \Theta_k \rangle$. Since S is firing for C' , we have that Θ_k contains the update $\text{upd} = (a, v)(P_{hr_i}, \text{ff})(P_{hr_j}, \text{tt})$, by definition of $\text{LocalUpds}(R_k, \{P_{hr_i}\}, \Sigma_k)$. Here, the value v in (a, v) is justified by Prop. 1A. Since the rule in (3) is local and it does not have default actions, we have that $\text{DefUpds}(R_k, \{P_{hr_i}\}, \Sigma_k) = \emptyset$ and $\text{ExtTasks}(R_k, \{P_{hr_i}\}, \Sigma_k) = \varepsilon$. When the AbU semantics evolves with the rule (STEP) applied to the system S , performing an execution step (EXEC), the update upd is committed,

obtaining $\Sigma_k'' = \Sigma_k[v/a \text{ ff}/P_h r_i \text{ tt}/P_h r_j]$. The discovery phase launched during (STEP) computes $\Theta_k'' = \Theta_k \setminus \{\text{upd}\} \cup \text{DefUpds}(R_k, \{a, P_h r_i, P_h r_j\}, \Sigma_k'') \cup \text{LocalUpds}(R_k, \{a, P_h r_i, P_h r_j\}, \Sigma_k'')$. By definition of \mathcal{T} , and $\text{Next}(i) = j$, we have that $\text{firing}(P'') = P_h r_j$. Hence, we have that Θ_k'' is a superset of $\text{DefUpds}(R_k, \{P_h r_j\}, \Sigma_k'') \cup \text{LocalUpds}(R_k, \{P_h r_j\}, \Sigma_k'')$. The last two requirements of the Def. 1 are satisfied by the definition of (STEP), that guarantees to perform the discovery of $T = \text{ExtTasks}(R_k, \{a, P_h r_i, P_h r_j\}, \Sigma_k)$ by applying the rule (DISC) with T on all nodes $w \in [1..n] \setminus \{k\}$. This means that $S'' = \mathbb{S}[R_k \langle \Sigma_k'', \Theta_k'' \rangle \gg R_k \langle \Sigma_k, \Theta_k \rangle]$ is firing for $C''' = C'[\Gamma : P \gg \Gamma[v/a] : P'']$. Furthermore, the only attribute modified in Γ is a , which is updated with the value v by the AbU semantics in Σ_k'' . Hence, we also have that $S'' \succeq C'''$. Since the derivation tree for $\Gamma[v/a] : P'' \xrightarrow{\delta} \Gamma[v/a]' : P'$ is smaller than the derivation tree for $\Gamma : P \xrightarrow{\delta} \Gamma[v/a]' : P'$, by inductive hypothesis we have that there exists S' such that $S' \succeq C'''$ and S' is firing for C''' , noting that $C''' = C''[\Gamma[v/a] : P'' \gg \Gamma[v/a]' : P']$, which concludes the proof for this case.

Case (AWARE). Then: $P = [II]P''$, for some P'' and II such that $\Gamma \models II$, given $\Gamma : P'' \xrightarrow{\delta} \Gamma' : P'$. Let $P_h r_i = \text{firing}(P)$ be the firing rule of P and $j = \text{Next}(i)$. The translation of P generates the following AbU rule:

$$P_h r_i \text{ Vars}(II) (P_h r_i = \top \wedge \mathcal{T}(II)) : P_h r_i \leftarrow \perp P_h r_j \leftarrow \top \quad (4)$$

We assumed that $\Gamma : P$ is the AbC component $\Gamma_k' : P_k'$ of C' , so we are on the node k of the AbU translation, i.e., $R_k \langle \Sigma_k, \Theta_k \rangle$. Since \mathbb{S} is firing for C' , we have that Θ_k contains the update $\text{upd} = (P_h r_i, \text{ff})(P_h r_j, \text{tt})$, by definition of $\text{LocalUpds}(R_k, \{P_h r_i\}, \Sigma_k)$. Since the rule in (4) is local and it does not have default actions, we have that $\text{DefUpds}(R_k, \{P_h r_i\}, \Sigma_k) = \emptyset$ and $\text{ExtTasks}(R_k, \{P_h r_i\}, \Sigma_k) = \varepsilon$. When the AbU semantics evolves with the rule (STEP) applied to the system \mathbb{S} , performing an execution step (EXEC), the update upd is committed, obtaining $\Sigma_k'' = \Sigma_k[\text{ff}/P_h r_i \text{ tt}/P_h r_j]$. The discovery phase launched during (STEP) computes $\Theta_k'' = \Theta_k \setminus \{\text{upd}\} \cup \text{DefUpds}(R_k, \{P_h r_i, P_h r_j\}, \Sigma_k'') \cup \text{LocalUpds}(R_k, \{P_h r_i, P_h r_j\}, \Sigma_k'')$. By definition of \mathcal{T} , and $\text{Next}(i) = j$, we have that $\text{firing}(P'') = P_h r_j$. Hence, we have that Θ_k'' is a superset of $\text{DefUpds}(R_k, \{P_h r_j\}, \Sigma_k'') \cup \text{LocalUpds}(R_k, \{P_h r_j\}, \Sigma_k'')$. The last two requirements of Def. 1 are satisfied by the definition of (STEP), guaranteeing to perform the discovery of $T = \text{ExtTasks}(R_k, \{P_h r_i, P_h r_j\}, \Sigma_k)$ by applying the rule (DISC) with T on all nodes $w \in [1..n] \setminus \{k\}$. This means that $S'' = \mathbb{S}[R_k \langle \Sigma_k'', \Theta_k'' \rangle \gg R_k \langle \Sigma_k, \Theta_k \rangle]$ is firing for $C''' = C'[\Gamma : P \gg \Gamma : P'']$. Furthermore, no attributes of Γ are modified (only auxiliary resources added by the translation are involved in the update). Hence, we also have that $S'' \succeq C'''$. Since the derivation tree for $\Gamma : P'' \xrightarrow{\delta} \Gamma' : P'$ is smaller than the derivation tree for $\Gamma : P \xrightarrow{\delta} \Gamma' : P'$, by inductive hypothesis we have that there exists S' such that $S' \succeq C'''$ and S' is firing for C''' , noting that $C''' = C''[\Gamma : P'' \gg \Gamma' : P']$, which concludes the proof for this case.

Case (SUM). Then: $P = P_a + P_b$, for some P_a and P_b , given $\Gamma : P_a \xrightarrow{\delta} \Gamma' : P'$. The symmetric case is analogous. Let $P_{hr_i} = \text{firing}(P)$ be the firing rule of P , $j = \text{Next}(i)$ and $w = \text{Next}(j)$. The translation of P generates the following AbU rules:

$$\begin{aligned} P_{hr_i} (P_{hr_i} = \top) : P_{hr_i} \leftarrow \perp P_{hr_j} \leftarrow \top \\ P_{hr_i} (P_{hr_i} = \top) : P_{hr_i} \leftarrow \perp P_{hr_k} \leftarrow \top \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

We assumed that $\Gamma : P$ is the AbC component $\Gamma'_k : P'_k$ of C' , so we are on the node k of the AbU translation, i.e., $R_k \langle \Sigma_k, \Theta_k \rangle$. Since S is firing for C' , we have that Θ_k contains the update $\text{upd} = (P_{hr_i}, \text{ff})(P_{hr_j}, \text{tt})$, by definition of $\text{LocalUpds}(R_k, \{P_{hr_i}\}, \Sigma_k)$, and assuming that AbC and AbU schedulers make the same decisions (i.e., P_a and the first rule in 5 are chosen). Since the rules in (5) are local and they do not have default actions, we have that $\text{DefUpds}(R_k, \{P_{hr_i}\}, \Sigma_k) = \emptyset$ and $\text{ExtTasks}(R_k, \{P_{hr_i}\}, \Sigma_k) = \varepsilon$. When the AbU semantics evolves with the rule (STEP) applied to the system S , performing an execution step (EXEC), the update upd is committed, obtaining $\Sigma''_k = \Sigma_k[\text{ff}/P_{hr_i} \text{ tt}/P_{hr_j}]$. The discovery phase launched during (STEP) computes $\Theta''_k = \Theta_k \setminus \{\text{upd}\} \cup \text{DefUpds}(R_k, \{P_{hr_i}, P_{hr_j}\}, \Sigma''_k) \cup \text{LocalUpds}(R_k, \{P_{hr_i}, P_{hr_j}\}, \Sigma''_k)$. By definition of \mathcal{T} , and $\text{Next}(i) = j$, we have that $\text{firing}(P'') = P_{hr_j}$. Hence, we have that Θ''_k is a superset of $\text{DefUpds}(R_k, \{P_{hr_j}\}, \Sigma''_k) \cup \text{LocalUpds}(R_k, \{P_{hr_j}\}, \Sigma''_k)$. The last two requirements of the Def. 1 are satisfied by the definition of (STEP), that guarantees to perform the discovery of $T = \text{ExtTasks}(R_k, \{P_{hr_i}, P_{hr_j}\}, \Sigma_k)$ by applying the rule (DISC) with T on all nodes $w \in [1..n] \setminus \{k\}$. This means that $S'' = S[R_k \langle \Sigma''_k, \Theta''_k \rangle \gg R_k \langle \Sigma_k, \Theta_k \rangle]$ is firing for $C''' = C'[\Gamma : P \gg \Gamma : P_a]$. Furthermore, no attributes of Γ are modified (only auxiliary resources added by the translation are involved in the update). Hence, we also have that $S'' \succeq C'''$. Since the derivation tree for $\Gamma : P_a \xrightarrow{\delta} \Gamma' : P'$ is smaller than the derivation tree for $\Gamma : P \xrightarrow{\delta} \Gamma' : P'$, by inductive hypothesis we have that there exists S' such that $S' \succeq C'''$ and S' is firing for C'' , noting that $C'' = C'''[\Gamma : P_a \gg \Gamma' : P']$, which concludes the proof for this case (the symmetric counterpart where the scheduler choses P_b is analogous).

Case (REC). Then: $P = K$, given $K \triangleq P_w$, with $w \in [1..n]$, and $\Gamma : P_w \xrightarrow{\delta} \Gamma' : P'$. Let $P_{hr_i} = \text{firing}(P)$ be the firing rule of P . The translation of P generates the following AbU rule:

$$P_{hr_i} (P_{hr_i} = \top) : P_{hr_i} \leftarrow \perp P_{kr_0} \leftarrow \top \quad (6)$$

We assumed that $\Gamma : P$ is the AbC component $\Gamma'_k : P'_k$ of C' , so we are on the node k of the AbU translation, i.e., $R_k \langle \Sigma_k, \Theta_k \rangle$. Since S is firing for C' , we have that Θ_k contains the update $\text{upd} = (P_{hr_i}, \text{ff})(P_{wr_0}, \text{tt})$, by definition of $\text{LocalUpds}(R_k, \{P_{hr_i}\}, \Sigma_k)$. Since the rule in (6) is local and it does not have default actions, we have that $\text{DefUpds}(R_k, \{P_{hr_i}\}, \Sigma_k) = \emptyset$ and $\text{ExtTasks}(R_k, \{P_{hr_i}\}, \Sigma_k) = \varepsilon$. When the AbU semantics evolves with the rule (STEP) applied to the system S , performing an execution step (EXEC), the update upd is committed, obtaining $\Sigma''_k = \Sigma_k[\text{ff}/P_{hr_i} \text{ tt}/P_{wr_0}]$.

The discovery phase launched during (STEP) computes $\Theta_k'' = \Theta_k \setminus \{\text{upd}\} \cup \text{DefUpds}(R_k, \{P_h r_i, P_w r_0\}, \Sigma_k'') \cup \text{LocalUpds}(R_k, \{P_h r_i, P_w r_0\}, \Sigma_k'')$. By definition of \mathcal{T} , we have that $\text{firing}(P_w) = P_w r_0$. Hence, we have that Θ_k'' is a superset of $\text{DefUpds}(R_k, \{P_w r_0\}, \Sigma_k'') \cup \text{LocalUpds}(R_k, \{P_w r_0\}, \Sigma_k'')$. The last two requirements of the Def. 1 are satisfied by the definition of (STEP), that guarantees to perform the discovery of $T = \text{ExtTasks}(R_k, \{P_h r_i, P_w r_0\}, \Sigma_k)$ by applying the rule (DISC) with T on all nodes $w \in [1..n] \setminus \{k\}$. This means that $S'' = S[R_k \langle \Sigma_k'', \Theta_k'' \rangle \gg R_k \langle \Sigma_k, \Theta_k \rangle]$ is firing for $C''' = C'[\Gamma : P \gg \Gamma : P_w]$. Furthermore, no attributes of Γ are modified (only auxiliary resources added by the translation are involved in the update). Hence, we also have that $S'' \succeq C'''$. Since the derivation tree for $\Gamma : P_w \xrightarrow{\delta} \Gamma' : P'$ is smaller than the derivation tree for $\Gamma : P \xrightarrow{\delta} \Gamma' : P'$, by inductive hypothesis we have that there exists S' such that $S' \succeq C''$ and S' is firing for C'' , noting that $C'' = C'''[\Gamma : P_w \gg \Gamma' : P']$, which concludes the proof for this case.

Lemma 2 (Helper). *Consider a AbC component $C = \Gamma_1 : P_1 \parallel \dots \parallel \Gamma_n : P_n$ and a AbU system $S = R_1 \langle \Sigma_1, \Theta_1 \rangle \parallel \dots \parallel R_n \langle \Sigma_n, \Theta_n \rangle$, such that $R_i = \mathcal{T}^i(P_i)$, for $i \in [1..n]$. Let C'' be a residual of C . If $S \succeq C''$ and S is firing for C'' , then for all C' such that $C'' \xrightarrow{\Pi(v)} C'$, for some Π and v , there exists a AbU system S' such that $S \rightarrow^* S'$, $S' \succeq C'$ and S' is firing for C' .*

Proof. Since C'' is a residual of C , it is of the form $\Gamma_1'' : P_1'' \parallel \dots \parallel \Gamma_n'' : P_n''$, with $\Gamma_i'' : P_i''$ residuals of $\Gamma_i : P_i$, for $i \in [1..n]$. Then, $C' = \Gamma_1' : P_1' \parallel \dots \parallel \Gamma_n' : P_n'$, given $\Gamma_i'' : P_i'' \xrightarrow{\Pi(v)} \Gamma_i' : P_i'$, for each $i \in [1..n]$. By Lem. 1, we have that there exists S^1 such that $S \rightarrow^* S^1$, $S^1 \succeq C^1$ and S^1 is firing for C^1 , where $C^1 = C''[\Gamma_1'' : P_1'' \gg \Gamma_1' : P_1']$. Applying again Lem. 1, we have that there exists S^2 such that $S^1 \rightarrow^* S^2$, $S^2 \succeq C^2$ and S^2 is firing for C^2 , where $C^2 = C^1[\Gamma_2'' : P_2'' \gg \Gamma_2' : P_2']$. We can repeat this reasoning $n - 2$ times and prove that there exists S^n such that $S^{n-1} \rightarrow^* S^n$, $S^n \succeq C^n$ and S^n is firing for C^n , where $C^n = C^{n-1}[\Gamma_n'' : P_n'' \gg \Gamma_n' : P_n']$. Note that, for each step i , with $i \in [1..n]$, we have that no modifications of the state of the nodes j , with $j \in [1..n] \setminus \{i\}$, are made on attributes and rule flags (by Prop. 1C). At this point we can note that $C^n = C'$, hence we have that $S' \succeq C'$ and S' is firing for C' , taking $S' = S^n$.

Lemma 3. *Consider a AbC component $C = \Gamma_1 : P_1 \parallel \dots \parallel \Gamma_n : P_n$ and a AbU system $S = R_1 \langle \Sigma_1, \Theta_1 \rangle \parallel \dots \parallel R_n \langle \Sigma_n, \Theta_n \rangle$, such that $R_i = \mathcal{T}^i(P_i)$, for $i \in [1..n]$. Let C'' be a residual of C . If $S \succeq C''$ and S is firing for C'' , then for all C' such that $C'' \xrightarrow{\lambda} C'$ there exists a AbU system S' such that $S \rightarrow^* S'$, $S' \succeq C'$ and S' is firing for C' .*

Proof. Since C'' is a residual of C , it is of the form $\Gamma_1'' : P_1'' \parallel \dots \parallel \Gamma_n'' : P_n''$, with $\Gamma_i'' : P_i''$ residuals of $\Gamma_i : P_i$, for $i \in [1..n]$. Let $C_r = \Gamma_2'' : P_2'' \parallel \dots \parallel \Gamma_n'' : P_n''$, i.e., $C'' = \Gamma_1'' : P_1'' \parallel C_r$. The proof is by case analysis on λ .

Case $\lambda = \tau$. Then, $C' = \Gamma_1' : P_1' \parallel C_r$, given $\Gamma_1'' : P_1'' \xrightarrow{\overline{\Pi}(v)} \Gamma_1' : P_1'$, for some Π and v , and $C_r \xrightarrow{\Pi(v)}$, i.e., $\Gamma_i'' : P_i'' \xrightarrow{\Pi(v)}$ for each $i \in [2..n]$. By Lem. 1,

we have that there exists S' such that $S \rightarrow^* S'$, $S' \succeq C^1$ and S' is firing for C^1 , where $C^1 = C''[\Gamma_1'' : P_1'' \gg \Gamma_1' : P_1']$. Since no modifications of the state of the node i , with $i \in [2..n]$, are made on attributes and rule flags (by Prop. 1C), we have that $S' \succeq C_r$ and S' is firing for C_r . Since C_r is unmodified, we can conclude that $S' \succeq C'$ and S' is firing for C' .

Case $\lambda = \overline{\Pi}\langle v \rangle$. Then, $C' = \Gamma_1' : P_1' \parallel C_r'$, given $\Gamma_1'' : P_1'' \xrightarrow{\overline{\Pi}\langle v \rangle} \Gamma_1' : P_1'$, for some Π and v , $C_r' = \Gamma_2' : P_2' \parallel \dots \parallel \Gamma_n' : P_n'$ and $C_r \xrightarrow{\Pi(v)} C_r'$, i.e., $\Gamma_i'' : P_i'' \xrightarrow{\Pi(v)} \Gamma_i' : P_i'$ for each $i \in [2..n]$. By Lem. 1, there exists S^1 such that $S \rightarrow^* S^1$, $S^1 \succeq C^1$ and S^1 is firing for C^1 , where $C^1 = C''[\Gamma_1'' : P_1'' \gg \Gamma_1' : P_1']$. Since no modifications of the state of the nodes i , with $i \in [2..n]$, are made on attributes and rule flags (by Prop. 1C), we have that $S^1 \succeq C_r$ and S^1 is firing for C_r . Then, applying Lem. 2 on C_r , we have that there exists S' such that $S' \succeq C_r'$ and S' is firing for C_r' . So, we can conclude that $S' \succeq C'$ and S' is firing for C' , noting that $C' = C^1[C_r \gg C_r']$.

Case $\lambda = \Pi(v)$. Then, $C' = \Gamma_1' : P_1' \parallel C_r'$, given $\Gamma_1'' : P_1'' \xrightarrow{\Pi(v)} \Gamma_1' : P_1'$, for some Π and v , $C_r' = \Gamma_2' : P_2' \parallel \dots \parallel \Gamma_n' : P_n'$ and $C_r \xrightarrow{\Pi(v)} C_r'$, i.e., $\Gamma_i'' : P_i'' \xrightarrow{\Pi(v)} \Gamma_i' : P_i'$ for each $i \in [1..n]$. By Lem. 1, there exists S^1 such that $S \rightarrow^* S^1$, $S^1 \succeq C^1$ and S^1 is firing for C^1 , where $C^1 = C''[\Gamma_1'' : P_1'' \gg \Gamma_1' : P_1']$. Since no modifications of the state of the nodes i , with $i \in [2..n]$, are made on attributes and rule flags (by Prop. 1C), we have that $S^1 \succeq C_r$ and S^1 is firing for C_r . Then, applying Lem. 2 on C_r , we have that there exists S' such that $S' \succeq C_r'$ and S' is firing for C_r' . So, we can conclude that $S' \succeq C'$ and S' is firing for C' , noting that $C' = C^1[C_r \gg C_r']$.

Lemma 4 (Input). *Consider a AbC component C and its corresponding AbU encoding $S = \mathcal{T}(C)$. Then there exists S' such that $S \rightarrow^* S'$, S' is firing for C and $S' \succeq C$.*

Proof. Suppose that C is composed by n components, i.e., $C = \Gamma_1 : P_1 \parallel \dots \parallel \Gamma_n : P_n$. Consider its AbU translation $S = R_1\langle \Sigma_1, \Theta_1 \rangle \parallel \dots \parallel R_n\langle \Sigma_n, \Theta_n \rangle = \mathcal{T}(C)$. By definition, we have that $R_i = \mathcal{T}^i(P_i)$, for $i \in [1..n]$. The translation yields n (one for each component) initial rule flags P_1r_0, \dots, P_nr_0 , initially set to ff (i.e., $\Sigma_i(P_ir_0) = \text{ff}$, for $i \in [1..n]$). Suppose to perform an input (INPUT) on the node 1, setting P_1r_0 to tt, namely $\Sigma_1' = \Sigma_1[\text{tt}/P_1r_0]$ and $\Theta_1 = \text{DefUpds}(R_1, \{P_1r_0\}, \Sigma_1') \cup \text{LocalUpds}(R_1, \{P_1r_0\}, \Sigma_1')$. The input is wrapped into the AbU rule (STEP), that guarantees to perform the discovery of $T^1 = \text{task}_1 \dots \text{task}_w = \text{ExtTasks}(R_1, \{P_1r_0\}, \Sigma_1')$, by applying the rule (DISC) with T^1 on all nodes $j \in [2..n]$. This potentially initialize the pools of other nodes, namely for all $j \in [2..n]$ we have that $\Theta_j = \{\llbracket \text{act} \rrbracket \Sigma_j \mid \exists l \in [1..w]. \text{task}_l = @\varphi : \text{act} \wedge \Sigma_j \models \varphi\}$. Hence we have $S \xrightarrow{T^1} S_1$, where $S_1 = R_1\langle \Sigma_1', \Theta_1 \rangle \parallel R_2\langle \Sigma_2, \Theta_2 \rangle \parallel \dots \parallel R_n\langle \Sigma_n, \Theta_n \rangle$. Now, we can perform another input (INPUT) on the node 2, setting P_2r_0 to tt, namely $\Sigma_2' = \Sigma_2[\text{tt}/P_2r_0]$ and $\Theta_2' = \Theta_2 \cup \text{DefUpds}(R_2, \{P_2r_0\}, \Sigma_2') \cup \text{LocalUpds}(R_2, \{P_2r_0\}, \Sigma_2')$. The input is wrapped into the AbU rule (STEP), that guarantees to perform the dis-

covery of $T^2 = \text{task}_1 \dots \text{task}_m = \text{ExtTasks}(R_2, \{P_2 r_0\}, \Sigma'_2)$, by applying the rule (Disc) with T^2 on all nodes $j \in [1..n] \setminus \{2\}$. This potentially enlarges the pools of other nodes, namely for all $j \in [1..n] \setminus \{2\}$ we have that $\Theta'_j = \Theta_j \cup \{\llbracket \text{act} \rrbracket \Sigma_j \mid \exists l \in [1..m]. \text{task}_l = @\varphi : \text{act} \wedge \Sigma_j \models \varphi\}$. Hence we have $S^1 \xrightarrow{\blacktriangleright T^2} S^2$, where $S^2 = R_1 \langle \Sigma'_1, \Theta'_1 \rangle \parallel R_2 \langle \Sigma'_2, \Theta'_2 \rangle \parallel \dots \parallel R_n \langle \Sigma_n, \Theta'_n \rangle$. We can repeat this reasoning $n - 2$ times, with $n - 2$ subsequent input steps, obtaining S^n such that $S^{n-1} \xrightarrow{\blacktriangleright T^n} S^n$. Since we are not performing execution steps (EXEC), the pools of the nodes can only be enlarged. Hence, it is easy to note that all requirements of Def. 1 are satisfied, implying that S^n is firing for C . Furthermore, no attributes of C are modified, so $S^n \succeq C$. Finally, setting $S' = S^n$ and $\rightarrow^* = \xrightarrow{\blacktriangleright T^1} \dots \xrightarrow{\blacktriangleright T^n}$, we can conclude that $S \rightarrow^* S'$, S' is firing for C and $S' \succeq C$.

Theorem 1 (AbC to AbU correctness)

Proof. Suppose that C is composed by n components, i.e., $C = \Gamma_1 : P_1 \parallel \dots \parallel \Gamma_n : P_n$. Consider its AbU translation $S = R_1 \langle \Sigma_1, \Theta_1 \rangle \parallel \dots \parallel R_n \langle \Sigma_n, \Theta_n \rangle = \mathcal{T}(C)$. By definition, we have that $R_i = \mathcal{T}^i(P_i)$, for $i \in [1..n]$. By Lem. 4, we have that there exists S'' such that $S \rightarrow^* S''$, S'' is firing for C and $S'' \succeq C$. This, in particular, means that each P_i of C is ready to execute. Now, suppose that $C \rightarrow^* C'$ comprises m semantic steps, namely $C \xrightarrow{\lambda_1} C^1 \xrightarrow{\lambda_2} \dots \xrightarrow{\lambda_m} C'$, for some component labels $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_m$. Applying Lem. 3, we have that there exists S^1 such that $S'' \rightarrow^* S^1$, $S^1 \succeq C^1$ and S^1 is firing for C^1 . We can repeat this reasoning $m - 1$ times and prove that there exists S^m such that $S^{m-1} \rightarrow^* S^m$, $S^m \succeq C^m$ and S^m is firing for C^m (which coincides with C'). By composition of all (STEP) rules (given by Lem. 3) we can conclude that $S'' \rightarrow^* S'$ such that $S' \succeq C'$, for $S' = S^m$.

References

1. Marino Miculan and Michele Pasqua. A calculus for attribute-based memory updates. In Antonio Cerone and Peter Ölveczky, editors, *Theoretical Aspects of Computing - ICTAC 2021 - 18th International Colloquium, Nur-Sultan, Kazakhstan, Sep. 6-10, 2021, Proceedings*, Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Springer, 2021.